

which they are induced. Elucidating the functions of these proteins can lead to understanding the mechanism underlying salt tolerance. These proteins may also offer a convenient tool for molecular screening of germplasm. □

Variability in salt tolerance of accessions of wild rice species *Oryza punctata* and *O. officinalis*

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We have started a comprehensive salt tolerance screening program for all available wild rice germplasm. In the first phase, six accessions of *O. punctata*—three diploid ($2n=2x=24$ BB) and three tetraploid ($2n=4x=48$ BBCC)—and three diploid accessions of *O. officinalis* ($2n=2x=24$ CC) were tested in the glasshouse. We used the gravel culture technique and natural conditions of temperature (25/15 °C day/night temperature), 10 h light, and 60% relative humidity.

We raised seedlings by planting internode cuttings of stems in plastic pots filled with gravel and Hoagland nutrient solution. The pots were placed in another plastic pot containing nutrient solution to ensure a continuous nutrient supply to the plant and easy replacement of the solution. We planted three cuttings per pot and three pots/accession per species.

When leaves started to appear, we induced artificial salinity with a mixture

Space limitations prevent IRRN from publishing solely yield and yield component data from fertilizer field trials that are not conducted for at least two cropping seasons or at two differing sites. Publication of work in a single season or at one site is limited to manuscripts that provide either a) data and analysis beyond yield and yield components (e.g., floodwater parameters, microbial populations, soil mineral N dynamics, organic acid concentrations, or mineralization rates for organic N sources), or b) novel ways of interpreting yield and yield component data across seasons and sites.

Details of salt tolerance screening of different accessions of 2 wild rice species at 5 periods of growth (2, 4, 6, 8, and 10 wk).

Species	Accession no.	Chromosome number and genome	Survival (% of control)				
			2	4	6	8	10
<i>O. punctata</i>	103897 ^a	$2n = 2x = 24$	0	0	0	0	0
<i>O. punctata</i>	103917	BB	66	66	0	0	0
<i>O. punctata</i>	103903 ^b		33	0	-	-	-
<i>O. punctata</i>	105158	$2n=4x=48$	100	100	66	66	66
<i>O. punctata</i>	101389	BBCC	100	100	100	66	33
<i>O. punctata</i>	101408		100	100	66	33	0
<i>O. officinalis</i>	103286	$2n=2x=24$	100	100	66	66	33
<i>O. officinalis</i>	104973 ^a	CC	0	0	0	0	0
<i>O. officinalis</i>	105322 ^b		33	33	33	0	0
Basmati 370	Susceptible check		0	0	0	0	0
Jhona 349	Tolerant check		100	33	-	-	-

^aMost of the plants died at EC 5-8 dS/m. ^bMost of the plants died at EC 10-11 dS/m.

of Na₂SO₄ CaCl₂, MgCl₂, and NaCl at a ratio of 10:5:1:4 through a stepwise increase in electrical conductivity of 2 dS/m every other day until EC reached 12 dS/m. The entire saline solution was replaced with fresh solution semiweekly.

Susceptible check Basmati 370 died at the onset of EC 8 dS/m; tolerant check Jhona 349 died after 4 wk of growth at EC 12 dS/m (see table). Of the three accessions of *O. officinalis*, 104973 died between EC 5-EC 8 dS/m, 105322 survived for 6 wk, and 103286 survived for 10 wk at EC 12 dS/m.

Of the diploid accessions of *O. punctata*, only 103917 survived for 4 wk, while all three tetraploid accessions survived beyond 8 wk at EC 12 dS/m.

Accession 105158 survived for more than 12 wk in EC 12 dS/m. The plant was still in the vegetative phase and had only one tiller, but was healthy and green. We are not certain whether the vegetative growth was stressed by the weather during May-Aug, which is hot and dry under local conditions and a dormant period for wild rice species, or by salinity.

The study did indicate, however, that if many wild rice accessions are screened for salt tolerance, tremendous variability can be anticipated, and this can be used for salt tolerance improvement of cultivated rice varieties. As far as we are aware, this is the first report of salt tolerance in wild rice species other than *Porteresia coarctata*. Further studies are in progress. □

Integrated germplasm improvement—irrigated

PR110, a new bacterial blight (BB)-resistant rice variety for Punjab, India

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PR 106 is a predominant rice variety in the Punjab because of its high yield potential,

long slender grains, and duration that fits very well into a rice - wheat crop rotation. PR106 is, however, susceptible to BB, which is the most serious rice disease in the Punjab.

The State Variety Approval Committee has approved a new BB-resistant rice variety, PR110, for cultivation in the Punjab. PR110 was developed using the backcross

approach, with PR106 as recurrent parent. It inherited BB resistance from Patong 32, a tall photoperiod-sensitive variety from Malaysia. A dwarf homozygous BB-resistant F₃ line of TN1/Patong 32 was used as the female parent in the first cross with PR106, and followed by five recurrent backcrosses with PR106. PR110, from TN1/Patong 32//PR 106*⁶, was

Table 1. Yield and BB scores of PR110 and PR106, Punjab, India, 1988-91.

Year	Trials (no.)	PR110	PR106
<i>Mean yield (t/ha)</i>			
Research trials			
1988	2	7.6	7.4
1989	3	6.8	6.7
1990	4	7.5	7.0
1991	4	7.2	7.0
Mean	13	7.2	7.0
Adaptive trials			
1991	40	6.6	6.5
Overall mean	53	6.7	6.7
<i>BB score^a</i>			
Inoculated under field and artificial conditions			
1988		3	9
1989		3	9
1990		3	9
1991		3	9

^a Scored using the Standard evaluation system for rice.

Table 2. Agronomic and grain quality characters of PR110 and PR106.

Character	PR110	PR106
Plant height (cm)	115	113
Maturity days (no.)	145	145
Panicle-bearing tillers (no./m ²)	391	377
Spikelets (no./panicle)	202	198
Head rice recovery (%)	51.30	51.20
1000-grain wt (g)	17.70	17.90
Grain length (mm)	6.80	6.90
Grain breadth (mm)	1.97	2.04
Length-breadth ratio	3.43	3.38
Grain elongation ratio upon cooking	1.44	1.45
Amylose content (%)	24.70	25.30
Grain appearance	Translucent	Translucent

selected and evaluated for yield, agronomic, and grain quality characters.

Extensive tests showed that PR110 has yield potential equal to that of PR 106 (Table 1).

BB scores (Table 1) show that PR110 maintained its strong BB resistance to the Punjab isolate while PR106 was highly susceptible during 4 yr of testing under field and artificial inoculation conditions.

Agronomic and grain quality characters of PR110 are similar to those of PR 106 (Table 2). □

Hamzu 2, a high-yielding variety suitable for the cool east coastal area of DPR of Korea

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Hamzu 2 is a new rice variety with high and stable yield capacity under the conditions of the cool east coastal area of DPR of Korea.

The growth duration of Hamzu 2 is 172 d, which is 4-5 d shorter than that of check variety Pyongyang 15. Hamzu 2 has 3150 ± 50°C degree days accumulated temperature for growth above 10°C. When this variety was transplanted on 20 May in Hamzu region, it flowered 9-12 Aug and matured 2-5-30 Sep.

Hamzu 2 is 78 cm tall (without panicle), or 7 cm taller than the check. Its flag leaf is erect. Grain type is long-oval, spikelets are awnless, and its color is pale yellow.

Of five recommended varieties in this region, Hamzu 2 showed the highest cold tolerance in farmers' fields when serious cold damage occurred in Aug 1988.

It had the highest grain yield in regional yield trials during 1988-91 (see table); mean yield was 8.5 t/ha over 4 yr. It produced 1.6 t more grain/ha than the check in 1988. Grain number per panicle is significantly higher than that of the check.

Effective level of N fertilizer is 120-140 kg N/ha, and optimum spacing is 20 × 13 cm. Hamzu 2 has multiple resistance to insects and diseases, especially to blast and bacterial blight. □

Performance of Hamzu 2 in regional yield trials in DPR of Korea, 1988-91.

Variety	Panicles (no./hill)	Spikelets (no./panicle)	Filled grains (%)	1000-grain weight (g)	Grain yield (t/ha)
<i>1988</i>					
Hamzu 2	7.3	95.5	78.3	25.8	8.5
Pyongyang 15 (check)	8.7	73.8	64.1	26.5	6.9
<i>1989</i>					
Hamzu 2	7.3	109.2	71.7	28.2	8.6
Pyongyang 15	8.5	69.8	79.3	29.1	7.5
<i>1990</i>					
Hamzu 2	6.8	112.4	74.7	26.5	8.4
Pyongyang 15	7.8	78.9	74.0	27.8	7.6
<i>1991</i>					
Hamzu 2	9.6	79.6	73.7	27.3	8.6
Pyongyang 15	11.1	52.2	80.4	29.1	7.8

Rice germplasm for anaerobic seeding

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A serious constraint in direct seeded rice is unstable crop establishment, which is caused by limited O₂ supply to the germinating seeds in the flooded soil.

Rice varieties that establish well in flooded soil were recently identified. The coleoptile and mesocotyls of these varieties elongate well at low O₂ concentration. Some of the identified varieties originated from deepwater and aus cultures in Northeast India and

Bangladesh. It might be possible to use the varieties in waterlogged rainfed lowlands and in hydromorphic lands in West Africa.

I am collaborating with scientists in national agricultural research systems in Korea, the Philippines, and Vietnam to develop agronomic practices that can best utilize this particular physiological character. I am also testing whether the character can be incorporated into breeding lines.

Rice workers interested in using these varieties for agronomic trials, breeding direct seeded rice, or physiological analysis can obtain detailed information from the author. □